

Sample Name: PVC UV 5-10 μm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: 5-10 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 5,84 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $3,1 \times 10^{13}$ particles per gram
- 30342 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C_2ClH_3 (PVC) determined by XRF
- C=O peak (1717 cm^{-1}) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PVC spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
8,00	1,43	0,21	0,14	0,12	5,84	3.1×10^{13}	30342

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_2ClH_3	99,81
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Na	36
Al	443
Si	281
P	51
S	709
Ca	45
Cr	66
Fe	167
Ni	12
Cu	3
Zn	4
Mo	4

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

